

Received July 3, 2019, accepted July 18, 2019,

Digital Object Identifier 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2930544

Motion Control of Underwater Mine Explorer Robot UX-1: Field Trials

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This work was supported in part by the UNEXMIN project with funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant 690008, and in part by the RoboCity2030-DIH-CM Madrid Robotics Digital Innovation Hub ("Robotica aplicada a la mejora de la calidad de vida de los ciudadanos. fase IV"; S2018/NMT-4331), funded by "Programas de Actividades I+D en la Comunidad de Madrid" and cofunded by Structural Funds of the EU.

ABSTRACT In this paper, we present the results of a series of field trials conducted with an underwater vehicle in the increasingly complex underwater environments of the Kaatiala mine in Finland, the Idrija mine in Slovenia, and the Urgeiriça mine in Portugal. These field experiments have been performed to test and validate the motion control systems of the underwater explorer robot (UX-1), which are: a variable ballast system for buoyancy control, a variable pitch system for pitch control, and a propulsion system for depth and heading stabilization. The control method implemented is based on a state feedback linearization algorithm, previously tested and validated in a controlled water tank environment. Several experiments are shown which demonstrate the successful operation of the motion control systems in individual performance tests. Afterward, a full exploration and geo-scientific data collection mission is presented, where all of the motion control systems are active simultaneously during a deep dive to more than 100 m. The results obtained in the field tests demonstrate the effectiveness of the motion control systems and validate the UX-1 Robot platform as capable of performing the complex task of navigation and control in flooded mine environments.

INDEX TERMS Mine exploration, motion control, spherical robot, UNEXMIN.

I. INTRODUCTION

In past years, the decrease in mining activities due to low metal prices or negative environmental impact has led to an estimated 30,000 inactive or abandoned mines across European countries [1]. Several of these mines were poly-metallic ore deposits, where valuable metals often occurred together in different combinations, and most still contain a considerable amount of mineral reserves. Determining the viability of re-opening these abandoned mines represents a significant interest, due to the fact that Europe has near-complete dependency on the import of mineral raw materials considered critical minerals, or likely to become critical in the near future. With mine closures, the dewatering systems designed for mineral extraction usually stop. This induces the flooding of abandoned mine workings and raising of the water table level. Some of these mines have been closed hundreds

of years ago, which produce hazardous conditions and harsh environments for surveying and prospecting by means of human divers.

The UNEXMIN (UNderwater EXplorer for flooded MINes) project aims at developing a series of underwater autonomous robots that will form a multi-robot system designed to explore underground flooded mines for acquiring geo-scientific and topological data. The scientific data collected will be used by geologists, in order to assess the status of the mine sites and provide key information regarding feasibility and economic viability of re-opening.

The UX-1 Robot, seen in Fig. 1, is the first generation of underwater explorer robots for the UNEXMIN project. The robot has a spherical shape, with a diameter of only 620mm, and a robust aluminum cast hull allowing for a maximum working depth of 500 m. Such features have been chosen to meet the constraints of the targeted mines (old abandoned and flooded European mines). As the main objective of UX-1 Robot is to explore underground mines and to collect

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Saied Nahavandi.

FIGURE 1. UX-1 robot during field tests in Kaatiala mine, Finland.

geo-scientific and topological data, an array of scientific instruments is installed in the robot. The UX-1 Robot has the capability of measuring the water's temperature, pressure, pH and electrical conductivity, magnetic fields and gamma radiation levels. By using multispectral and UV fluorescence imaging units it is also capable of identifying various minerals located on the mine's walls.

Navigation in these enclosed and confined spaces is a rather complex and challenging task, which requires precise and robust motion control in all controllable degrees of freedom (DOF). Additionally, minimizing the vehicle energy usage during dives is essential in order to achieve the required dives times of up to 5 hours. The motion control systems designed for the UX-1 Robot are comprised of: a Propulsion System (PS), composed of eight thrusters in a cross manifold configuration that give the robot 5 DOF motion capabilities and a cruising speed of up to 0.5 m/s; a variable pitch system, used to control the pitch of the robot by shifting the center of gravity as to maintain the front of the robot towards the direction of movement; and a variable ballast system, used to compensate the change in buoyancy at different depths and aid in long vertical descents requiring virtually no power consumption.

Since the very early conception of the UNEXMIN project, it was decided that the UX-1 Robot prototypes would be validated in real life conditions (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of 6-7). To this effect, several flooded mines have been selected across Europe, with gradual increase in harshness of the conditions for field testing, with the general objective of acquiring mineralogical data, as well as generating a 3D model database of the explored mines.

A. SUMMARY OF THE TRIALS

Given the scale of the UNEXMIN project, a multidisciplinary technical team was assembled from different research institutions in Europe. Among these, the Mechatronics Research Group from Tampere University, in charge of the mechanical fabrication; the Centre for Robotics and Autonomous Systems from INESC-TEC, in charge of the perception

and electronics integration; and the Center for Automation and Robotics from the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, in charge of the guidance, navigation and control systems.

The first trials were carried out in June 2018 at the abandoned pegmatite mine Kaatiala, in Finland. This is a flooded open pit mine with a maximum depth of approximately 40 m, that continues into a number of underground drives. This open pit mine was selected as a first test site due to its easy accessibility, large tunnels without debris, non-complicated tunnel network and clear waters. Its depth allowed for easy recovery of the robot by a scuba-diver rescue team in case of malfunction. These initial trials focused on evaluating the performance of the basic motion control systems, e.g. the variable ballast system and the depth control, along with testing and calibrating scientific instrumentation.

The second field trials with the UX-1 Robot were done in September 2018, in a closed and partially flooded historical underground mercury mine at Idrija, Slovenia. This mine is listed as part of the UNESCO World Heritage site, which imposes additional constraints to the missions, since no-contact and no-damaging conditions are enforced. The Idrija mine is an underground mine with limited visibility and narrow passages. The enclosed environment presented an ideal scenario to validate the variable pitch system and heading control in murky waters and cluttered environments, in addition to the previously tested motion control systems. Moreover, the mine site provided important insight into the challenge of transporting and deploying the robot system in a genuine mine.

The third field trials were performed in March 2019 at the old uranium mine of Urgeiriça in Portugal. This mine presented similar underwater mine conditions as those found at the Idrija Mercury mine, such as murky waters, confined spaces and obstacles, without the complicated logistics of robot deployment. At this mine, the mission objectives were to test UX-1 Robot in a deep underground mine with accessible entrances to numerous mine levels. The structure of the mine provided the opportunity to test the performance with all the motion control systems activated simultaneously.

B. RELATED WORK

A great deal of research has been conducted on underwater vehicle systems that pursued exploration, navigation, and 3D mapping of underwater environments [2], [3]. Most of them addressed open water scenarios or large vertical shafts, which posed virtually no limitation on the size of the underwater vehicles. However, research projects have shown a growing interest in applications focused in confined unknown spaces where AUVs have been developed to tackle this problem.

The authors in [4] and [5] tested an underwater Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) to map and explore the underground water cisterns at the islands of Malta and Gozo. The underwater vehicle used was a VideoRay Pro III micro ROV, which had a length of 0.305 m. This small size allowed navigation through the narrow water cistern access points, commonly found in the aforementioned islands. The vehicle

was equipped with three thrusters, two forward and one vertical, which allowed movement in 3 DOF. A scanning sonar was used, but was limited to a range of 6 m and only 2D maps were obtained. Despite these limitations, the authors successfully implemented Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) algorithms in real time.

The SPARUS AUV [6] was a small, torpedo shaped underwater vehicle with 3 DOF motion control. Its dimensions were 1.22 m in length by 0.23 m in diameter with an operating time of up to 5 hours. The SPARUS AUV was used in [7] to survey the underwater cave complex “Coves de Cala Viuda,” in Spain, and provide acoustic, optical, and inertial measurements for research in autonomous navigation. However, the maximum depth was limited to 50 m which is not suitable for exploration of deep underwater environments.

The DEPTHX (DEep Phreatic THERmal eXplorer) project [8]–[10] had the primary objective of using an autonomous vehicle to explore and characterize the unique biology of the Sistema Zacatón cenotes. Similar to the UX-1 Robot, it was designed with an ellipsoidal shape to minimize the potential of it becoming snagged. Nevertheless, the operating environment consisted of wide shafts, between 50 m and 150 m in diameter, which allowed the limitation-free design with no significant restrictions on the size of the underwater vehicle (which measured approximately 1.5 m in height and 1.9 m in length and width). The cruising speed of the vehicle was 0.2 m/s and the operating time was approximately 4 hours. Autonomous exploration and 3D mapping was demonstrated, but was limited to vertical descent of large shafts.

NASA astrobiologists have developed Project SIMPLE (Sub-Ice Marine and PLANetary-analog Ecosystems). It aimed to use the McMurdo Ice Shelf as a proxy for theoretical ocean-like conditions under the ice of Europa, one of the moons of Jupiter where scientists believe there may be the best chance of finding biological specimens [11]. To this effect, several underwater vehicles have been deployed and recovered from ice boreholes for the navigation and exploration of ice-covered waters.

Based on the DEPTHX vehicle, the ENDURANCE (Environmentally Non-Disturbing Under-ice Robotic ANTarctic Explorer) AUV [12], [13] was designed to operate in a unique and extreme environment, the frozen waters of Lake Bonney in Taylor Valley. The ENDURANCE mission goals included traversing a 1 km × 2 km lake, obtaining a full 3D synoptic chemical profile, and high-resolution mapping. There were two significant changes from the DEPTHX configuration: the removal of the variable buoyancy system, which required improving the depth control of the vehicle using the vertical thrusters; and a different navigation strategy, where instead of sonar-based SLAM, ENDURANCE uses DVL/Inertial dead-reckoning augmented with an iUSBL whose transponder was hung underneath the melt hole.

The authors in [14] developed SCINI (Submersible Capable of under Ice Navigation and Imaging), a small torpedo shaped ROV with a length of 1.4 m and diameter of 15 cm,

designed to fit through a 20 cm hole in the ice. The vehicle was able to survey in water depths of up to 300 m, with forward speeds of up to 7.5 km/h, whilst Deep SCINI [15] was a 2000 m depth-qualified vehicle with design elements taken from the original SCINI. Similarly, the ICEFIN [16] was an under-ice ROV designed for deployment directly through ice which could be tens to hundreds of meters thick.

From the results obtained with the ENDURANCE AUV, the ARTEMIS [17], [18] was developed to provide high resolution sea floor imagery. It reached a maximum speed of 9 km/h with an operating time of up to 25 hours and a maximum depth rating of 5000 m. Moreover, the vehicle had a modular payload designed to operate in various missions, such as seabed mapping, oceanographic survey, search and rescue, oil and gas survey, and others. As was the case with DEPTHX and ENDURANCE, the ARTEMIS was not suitable for exploration of confined environments due to its torpedo shape with the length of 5 m.

The SUNFISH AUV [19] was a 6 DOF vehicle capable of on-line SLAM with obstacle avoidance and real-time path planning. It was built based on the earlier work by Stone Aerospace with the DEPTHX, ENDURANCE and ARTEMIS. It had the capability to integrate additional payloads for tasks such as water sampling or biogeochemical profiling. Its dimensions were 1.61 × 0.47 × 0.2 m with an operating time of 5 hours and a maximum depth rating of 200 m. The authors demonstrated autonomous navigation and path planning capabilities at the Peacock Springs cave system in Florida and mention survey of flooded mines as a potential application of SUNFISH AUV.

Several works can be found in the literature related to the UNEXMIN project [20] and the evolution of the UX-1 Robot. In [21], the authors presented the initial design of the mechanical subsystems and their functions, which were redesigned and upgraded using the structural strength analysis results in [22]. The design of the overall system was presented in [23], along with some preliminary simulation results. Once the fabrication UX-1 Robot platform had been concluded, several experimental underwater tests were performed in a water tank environment to compare the performance of linear and non-linear controllers on the UX-1 Robot motion systems [24]. Based on the results from the control systems, this work presents the field experiments performed with the UX-1 Robot in three flooded mines across Europe. These experiments include the test and validation of the different motion systems developed, several of which were not previously experimentally tested on the UX-1 Robot.

C. OUTLINE OF THE PAPER

The work presented is organized as follows: in Section II, the main components of the UX-1 Robot design will be presented, focusing on the previously untested motion control systems. In Section III, the equations of motion of the UX-1 Robot and control method used during the field trials is explained. Section IV details the architecture of the robotic underwater explorer, whilst field tests are reported in

Section V. Finally, results and discussions are carried out in Section VI with conclusions and future works presented in Section VII.

II. UX-1 ROBOT PLATFORM: DESIGN

The UX-1 Robot design, shown in Fig. 1, was developed according to strict restrictions in terms of size, weight, payload, and maneuverability, for the purpose of flooded mine exploration. The complete mechanical design process of the UX-1 Robot has been presented in several works, such as [21] and [22]. In this section, the mechanical designs of the motion control systems are presented and can be seen in Fig. 6.

A. EXTERNAL HULL AND MANIFOLDS

The closed-frame design of the external hull for the UX-1 Robot (Fig. 2) was comprised of three individual components: a toroid shaped central housing, and two aluminum side plates. Since the final design did not have a completely spherical shape, due to the external instrumentation, a thorough structural analysis using Finite Element Method was performed. These tests validated the non-ideal shape of the UX-1 Robot as capable of withstanding the high pressure conditions during the foreseen field operations [22].

FIGURE 2. Exploded view of robot aluminum external hull and side plates for sealing the watertight hull and fixing manifolds.

Among the available methods for manufacturing the central housing, the aluminum pouring casting method (Alloy AS7G06) was chosen, due to the complexity of the design; whereas, the side plates were manufactured by 5-axis machining as a monobloc (Alloy AW 7021). The PS for motion control of the UX-1 Robot was comprised of four thrusters in a cross manifold structure, rigidly attached to each side plate. The manifolds were integrated into syntactic foam to achieve a lateral spherical shape and provide any additional buoyancy required.

B. CENTRAL ROD

The central rod structure was a major component in the overall mechanical design of the hull. This element, shown in Fig. 3, was designed to be used as the mounting point

FIGURE 3. Side plates mounted on the central rod element of the UX-1.

for the side plates, as well as a common component for the variable ballast system and the variable pitch system.

This solution optimized the available space inside the UX-1 by integrating the oil reservoir tank, used by the variable ballast system, in the geometric center of the robot, and served as a mounting point for the variable pitch system.

C. VARIABLE PITCH SYSTEM

The mechanical design integrated the majority of the perception sensors, used for mapping and localization, pointing towards the front of the robot; thus, most of the navigation was expected to be done with the front of the UX-1 Robot facing towards the desired direction of movement. Since the general structure of the flooded mine environments intended to be explored mostly comprised of vertical shafts and/or horizontal tunnels, a motion control system for varying the pitch angle (along the horizontal axis y) was required.

FIGURE 4. Variable pitch system installed around the central rod.

To maximize the operation time during dives, a low power consumption design had to be implemented. As can be seen in Fig. 4 and Fig. 6(b), the Variable Pitch System (VPS) design consisted of a stepper motor with a bevel and worm gear setup, which rotates the battery module (three eccentrically placed 6S 16000 mAh LiPo Batteries) around the

central rod oil reservoir tank using a planetary gear fixed to the central rod. This shifting of a mass w.r.t the center of gravity of the vehicle generated a torque and in turn rotated the UX-1 Robot to a desired pitch angle, passively stabilizing the system.

D. VARIABLE BALLAST SYSTEM

The UX-1 was designed to explore mines with maximum depths of up to 500 m. If navigation and motion control were performed by relying solely on thruster actuation, the power consumption would have substantially decreased the operating time. The Variable Ballast System (VBS) was designed to adjust the buoyancy of the system during long distance vertical motions (e.g. in vertical shafts) compensating for buoyancy changes due to the pressure force on the hull [25].

FIGURE 5. Water cylinders and oil reservoir tank of the variable ballast system.

FIGURE 6. Real motion systems integrated into UX-1 robot. (a) variable ballast system; (b) variable pitch system.

The VBS motion control (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6(a)) was comprised of dual water inlet cylinders with aluminum pistons to divide water from oil, and an oil reservoir tank. When the UX-1 was at surface, the cylinders were filled with oil (with a density similar to water) and the oil reservoir tank was empty. In this state, the UX-1 had the maximum positive buoyancy available. When the VBS was initiated for descent, oil was pumped from the cylinders to the central oil tank, actuated by a brushless electric motor with a reduction gear which moved the pistons. This created suction in the water inlet

cylinders and were gradually filled with water, thus changing the weight of the vehicle and submerged by decreased buoyancy.

III. UX-1 ROBOT PLATFORM: MODEL AND CONTROL

The 6 DOF nonlinear dynamic model of the UX-1 Robot has been thoroughly explained in previous works, such as [21] and [24]. In these works, the theoretical expressions for calculating the parameters of the forces acting upon the vehicle (e.g. Rigid-Body forces, Hydrodynamic forces, and Hydrostatic forces) are derived and explained in detail, along with their experimental identification. This work broadens the previously used dynamic model by deriving the 6 DOF equations of motion using unit quaternions to represent the attitude of the vehicle.

A. EQUATIONS OF MOTION

The two reference frames adopted, $\{n\}$ and $\{b\}$, which can be seen in Fig. 7 are represented in world coordinates. Where $\{n\}$ denotes an inertial North-East-Down (NED) coordinate system with orthonormal basis $\{x_n, y_n, z_n\}$ and origin o_n ; and $\{b\}$ denotes a body-fixed reference frame with orthonormal basis $\{x_b, y_b, z_b\}$ and origin o_b .

FIGURE 7. Schematics of the developed underwater vehicle with the reference frames used in the equations of motion.

Using a quaternion attitude representation, the nonlinear equations of motion for an underwater vehicle, in $\{b\}$, can be expressed as:

$$\dot{\eta} = J_q^+(\eta)\mathbf{v} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{M}\dot{\mathbf{v}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{v})\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{D}(\mathbf{v})\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{g}(\eta) = \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (2)$$

with

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{M}_{RB} + \mathbf{M}_A \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{C}_{RB}(\mathbf{v}) + \mathbf{C}_A(\mathbf{v}) \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{v}) = \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{D}_n(\mathbf{v}) \quad (5)$$

where $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^7$ denotes the position and orientation vector in the NED coordinate system, $\mathbf{v} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ denotes the linear

FIGURE 8. General pose control scheme implemented on UX-1 robot for field experiments in underwater mines.

and angular velocity vectors in $\{b\}$, and $\tau \in \mathbb{R}^6$ describes the forces and moments acting on the vehicle in $\{b\}$. Moreover, $J_q^\dagger(\eta)$ is the left Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of the non-quadratic transformation matrix $J_q(\eta) \in \mathbb{R}^{7 \times 6}$. M , $C(v)$ and $D(v)$ denote the system inertia matrix, Coriolis-Centripetal term matrix and hydrodynamic damping matrix, respectively, whilst $g(\eta)$ is the vector of gravitational and buoyant forces [28]. The model matrices M , $C(v)$, $D(v)$ and $g(\eta)$, and their properties, have been previously defined for the UX-1 Robot in [24].

B. POSITION CONTROL

The overall position control system of the UX-1 Robot is shown in Fig. 8. It has been approached as a modular system for flexibility in testing and development. A force allocation module was used, in charge of interpreting the force requirements and distributing it to the actuators, followed by an outer position control module in charge of computing the reference force vector.

The force allocation approach was presented and developed in [24]. It was based on the mapping matrix, which gathers how the forces of the actuators generate effects on the control force vector of the system, by finding the explicit solution to the unconstrained Least-Squares optimization problem using Lagrange Multipliers. As can be seen in Fig. 8, the idea of this approach was that, given a reference force vector and the inverse of the mapping matrix (MMP), the velocity required by each thruster could be computed after multiplying by the thruster coefficient (TC).

In [24], several control methods were implemented and tested for the UX-1 Robot in a controlled tank environment. The control tests performed for a path tracking scenario showed that for the UX-1 Robot, the Nonlinear State Feedback Linearization (FL) controller yielded better position control performance when compared to the traditional Finite Horizon Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) control method. Thus, the State FL controller was chosen as the position control module to be used during the field testing experiments presented in this work. The basic principle of the FL control

method is the transformation of the nonlinear dynamics of an underwater vehicle into a set of independent chain of integrators. We consider the nonlinear kinematic and dynamic equations of an underwater vehicle in the quaternion representation form

$$\dot{\eta} = J_q(\eta)v \quad (6)$$

$$M\dot{v} + n(v, \eta) = \tau \quad (7)$$

where η and v are assumed to be measurable and n is defined as follows,

$$n(v, \eta) = C(v)v + D(v)v + g(\eta). \quad (8)$$

The control law is selected such that the nonlinearities of the system dynamics can be canceled out

$$\tau = M\lambda^b + n(v, \eta). \quad (9)$$

Differentiating (6) with respect to time and applying the control law (9) to the equations of motion in (7) yields

$$M(\dot{v} - \lambda^b) = MJ_q^\dagger(\eta) [\ddot{\eta} - \dot{J}_q(\eta)v - J_q(\eta)\lambda^b] = 0 \quad (10)$$

Choosing

$$\lambda^n = \dot{J}_q(\eta)v + J_q(\eta)\lambda^b \quad (11)$$

results in the linear decoupled system $M^*(\ddot{\eta} - \lambda^n) = 0$, where $M^* = J_q^\dagger(\eta)^\top M J_q^\dagger(\eta) > 0$. From (11) it can be concluded that the commanded acceleration in the body-fixed frame λ^b can be calculated by

$$\lambda^b = J_q^\dagger(\eta)[\lambda^n - \dot{J}_q(\eta)v] \quad (12)$$

and the commanded acceleration in the NED frame can be chosen as a PD control law with acceleration feedforward

$$\lambda^n = \ddot{\eta}_d - K_d \dot{\tilde{\eta}} - K_p \tilde{\eta} \quad (13)$$

where η_d is the desired position and orientation vector in NED, $\tilde{\eta} = \eta - \eta_d$ is the position and orientation tracking error and, K_p and K_d are positive definite diagonal matrices of the controller gains. These gains can be selected in order to set the desired error dynamics. In fact, with (13) the error dynamics $\ddot{\tilde{\eta}} + K_d \dot{\tilde{\eta}} + K_p \tilde{\eta} = 0$ are obtained.

IV. UX-1 ROBOT PLATFORM: ARCHITECTURE

In this section, the general architecture description of the robotic exploration system will be presented. The architecture is decomposed into three elements: 1. the system architecture will present an overall conceptual model of the set-up used during field testing, which includes user interfaces, communication protocols, and post-processing; 2. the hardware architecture will provide a representation of the electromechanical components integrated into the UX-1 Robot, such as sensors, scientific instrumentation, and motion control systems; and 3. the software architecture will focus on the high-level structure of the localization, navigation and control software components developed for the UX-1.

FIGURE 9. Field test system architecture conceptual model.

A. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture will vary depending on the environment conditions in the mine sites and the desired level of autonomy [23]. Nevertheless, an overall conceptual model of the system architecture, used during field testing, can be seen in Fig. 9. In general, the system architecture consisted of the UX-1 Robot, communication links, operator mission workstation, data management systems and the post-processing infrastructure.

In order to perform a full validation of the different sub-systems in unknown environments and reduce the risks of damage due to system failure, during these initial field trials, a direct communication link from the UX-1 Robot to the control room was available. The communication link had to be installed on-site for each mine site visited. It consisted of setting up a Gigabit fiber optic communication link between the launch site at water level (i.e. where the UX-1 would be deployed), a tether installed in the UX-1 made up of military grade fiber optic cable, and the control room, in some cases more than 200 m away.

In addition to the communication links, the operator mission workstation was set-up in the control room at each location. The operator mission workstation was comprised of all the support subsystems used during test dives. These included, a Human-Machine-Interface (HMI) station with peripherals used for teleoperation, in case of guided exploration or any malfunction; a system monitoring station where

different parameters of the UX-1 Robot could be supervised at all times, e.g., running processes, power consumption and depth; a 3D mapping and sensor visualization station where end-users, such as local geologists, mine personnel, and stakeholders could guide and examine in real time the mine structure and mineralogy; and a local data storage system for processing the acquired data between dives.

Multiple dives were performed at each mine site, which generated considerable amounts of data recorded after each trial (> 1 Tb). Since this information was intended for post-processing, to create high-fidelity 3D models and a database of mineralogical information from each mine site, all the data gathered during field tests was uploaded to an external central server.

B. HARDWARE ARCHITECTURE

In this section, the hardware architecture of the UX-1 will be presented, i.e., all components comprising the hardware system, their communication protocols, and interactions between them. The description of this architecture was essential, since it provided important information for system integration and software development. The hardware components, shown in Fig. 10, have been divided according to the tasks for which they were intended.

FIGURE 10. UX-1 robot hardware architecture components and communication protocols.

1) PERCEPTION

The perception components (Fig. 11(b)) were those used for measuring the attributes of the environment and extracting 3D information. The UX-1 Robot was equipped with the Tritech Micron Scanning Sonar (www.tritech.co.uk), an extremely compact 360° sonar scanner with a 75 m maximum range and RS485/232 communication protocols. Additionally, a Kongsberg M3 Multibeam Sonar (www.km.kongsberg.com), which generates both imaging and bathymetric data, was available for long distance precision mapping of up to 500 m range.

A structure from light system (SLS) was used to calculate the depth and surface point cloud information of the mine walls. This consisted of using five digital cameras with

FIGURE 11. Final 3D model of robot mechanical design (a) Left view (manifold system for propulsion and MSU), (b) Front view (scanning sonar, multibeam Sonar and SLS), (c) Right view (manifold system and camera), (d) Top view (camera and water sampling unit), (e) Bottom view (DVL, SMP, camera and PH sensors).

110° lens opening, each recording at 9 fps, with 2054×1544 image resolution, to calculate the deformation when light from a projected laser line struck surfaces [23].

Four light and laser projectors were used to illuminate with visible light, UV light and project a 1.0 W laser line. Synchronization with LED visible light, lasers and other triggers were handled by the master sync control component.

2) LOCALIZATION

The localization elements were used to estimate the position and orientation of the UX-1 Robot in the NED frame of reference for navigation and path following. For this task, the UX-1 Robot was equipped with a KVH 1750 (www.kvh.com) fiber optic Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU), with an RS-422 communication protocol, for feedback of linear accelerations and angular velocities installed inside the watertight hull, as well as an RDI Teledyne Workhorse Navigator 600 (<http://www.teledynemarine.com>) Doppler Velocity Logger (DVL), with Ethernet communication interface, for feedback of pressure, linear velocities and distance to bottom measurements (Fig. 11(e)).

3) MOTION

The motion systems on the UX-1 Robot used CAN Bus communications and include the PS, VPS, and the VBS.

Where the latter two have been previously introduced in Section II. The PS is responsible for the translation in the x, y, z axis and rotation in heading and roll. It is actuated by means of eight BlueRobotics T200 brushless electric motor thrusters (www.bluerobotics.com) divided equally on each manifold attached to the side plates (Fig. 11(a) and 11(c)). The PS thrusters and VBS pump motor velocities were controlled by VESC (<http://vedder.se/>) Electronic Speed Controllers.

4) SCIENTIFIC

The scientific instrumentation components integrated into the UX-1 Robot have been designed and fabricated specifically for this platform [20]. These include: a multi-spectral imaging unit (MSU) for mineralogical characterization; a water sampling unit; a Gamma Ray (GR) sensor for detecting radioactive minerals; a PH sensor and a sub-bottom profiler (SBP).

5) COMMUNICATION

The communication link to the main PC was done using a fiber optic tether cable. This tether was connected to a fiber optic transceiver/media converter which converted data signal between 10/100/1000Base-T and 1000Base-LX Gigabit Ethernet. Additionally, the on-board pc was equipped with a wireless module to allow communication with the robot without the need of a physical connection.

6) COMPUTING

The UX-1 Robot has a distributed computer system for on-board processing, interfaces and motion control. A Com Express Type 6 PC (i7-8850H processor at 2.6/4.3GHz with QM370 chipset) was installed as the on-board main CPU. This computer hosts the Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) algorithms, as well as data fusion algorithms and hardware drivers and interfaces.

Com Express Type 10 Dedicated CPUs (Intel Atom x7-E3950 quad core processor with 1.6GHz core frequency) were used in intensive specific sensor processing tasks. For instance, one sonar processing CPU, that was responsible for raw Multibeam sonar data pre-processing, provided a filtered output 3D point cloud that was integrated in the main computer [23]. Additionally, two more dedicated CPUs were used to extract 3D point cloud information from the SLS.

7) POWER

As mentioned in Section II-C, the battery module consisted three 6S 16000 mAh LiPo Batteries. The battery management system (BMS) was used to consistently monitor battery module parameters, such as charge, temperature, and current consumption, as well as, managing the distribution of power during the battery charging process.

C. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The control software architecture has been organized into three separate layers (see Fig. 12). Each layer was composed of multiple intercommunicating nodes, in a modular structure, that could be replaced, edited, and tested with minimal effect on other modules. This allowed for greater flexibility and eventual scalability.

FIGURE 12. Control software architecture developed for the UX-1 robot field trials.

The open source Robotic Operating System (ROS Kinetic distribution) middleware framework was used to handle intercommunication between processes. All nodes have been implemented in Python or C++ in the Com Express Type 6 main PC running the GNU/Linux operating system Ubuntu 16.04 LTS (Xenial).

The motion layer contained all the nodes related to the movement of the UX-1 Robot. This layer was composed of:

the HMI subsystem, for interfacing any commands sent by the human operator, e.g., take over manual control or command a specific waypoint; the GNC subsystem, in charge of deciding the overall movement strategy, computing trajectories in the form of waypoints and transforming these into force commands by the control strategy presented in Section III-B; the manager node, which received commands from the control nodes and distributed them depending on the mode of operation (i.e. teleoperated, autonomous, partial control); and the thruster allocation node, which implemented the force allocation module.

In the localization layer, developed by researchers at INESC-TEC (<https://www.inesctec.pt>), the 3D mapping node integrated the point cloud information obtained by the Tritech Scanning Sonar, the M3 Multibeam Sonar and the SLS. Additionally, the sensor fusion node implemented an Adaptive Extended Kalman Filter, to estimate the position, velocity and attitude of the UX-1 Robot by using data provided by DVL, IMU and pressure sensor [23]. The localization node will integrate a SLAM algorithm which receives the pose information of the sensor fusion and the mapping data from the 3D mapping and provides a corrected 3D map and global localization estimates. This SLAM implementation is still to be developed and field tested.

Lastly, the driver interface layer handled the communications between the software nodes and the hardware components. For the control software, two main interfaces were used. The VESC driver was used to send RPM commands the electronic speed controllers used for thruster actuators control (see IV-B3); and the CAN Communication driver translated standard ROS messages into CAN Bus socketcan messages to control the VPS, VBS and receive information from the BMS.

V. UX-1 ROBOT PLATFORM: FIELD EXPERIMENTS

The field experiments with the UX-1 Robot were performed in order to acquire data on the mineralogical composition of the mines, as well as to gather mapping data to build 3D models of the mines, of whom no structural information was available. Nevertheless, the operation and performance of the individual motion systems developed for the UX-1 Robot, were tested and validated in increasingly complex real-life environments.

Three flooded mines have been explored across Europe, with gradual increase in the harshness of the conditions (i.e. accessibility, extent of tunnel network system, potential for robot recovery in the case of malfunction, etc.). The first trial was carried out in the pegmatite mine Kaatiala, in Finland. The second test has been conducted in the historical Idrija mercury mine, in Slovenia. Lastly, the third trial was performed in the old uranium mine of Urgeiriça, in Portugal.

As previously mentioned, the robot was connected to the control room via a tether connection for real-time monitoring and visualization. These initial field tests were semi-autonomous, where an operator on the mission workstation teleoperated the UX-1 Robot in the horizontal axes $\{x, y\}$ and

occasionally the heading, while the depth of the robot was fully controlled with reference setpoints and the roll was fixed at $\phi = 0$ rad. This decision was made in order to allow local geologists and mine personnel to guide the exploration and acquire as much mineralogical and structural data as possible from the scientific instrumentation.

During the field experiments, a considerable number of dives were performed to test different system functions. This section will outline the main experiments performed on the new motion systems, at each mine site. The systems tested include the VBS, VPS and Heading control. The depth control was field validated as well, based on the previous knowledge acquired during the controlled environment testing in [24].

A. KAATIALA MINE, FINLAND

1) ENVIRONMENT DESCRIPTION

The Kaatiala mine is located in the Vassa province of western Finland. The exploitation of minerals, mainly quartz, started in the 19th century. Due to the needs of the steel-making industry during the Second World War, quarrying of pegmatite begun in 1942, followed soon afterwards by production of feldspar for the domestic ceramics industry. In 1968 mineral extraction from the mine became unprofitable and mining operations were ceased causing the mine to become flooded.

FIGURE 13. Top view of the Kaatiala Mine tunnel system used for the first field tests.

Kaatiala is a flooded open pit mine with maximum depth of approximately 40 m. The mine site is currently used as a tourist attraction for recreational scuba divers. There are three tunnel entrances varying in size and equipped with guide ropes and a diving bell (see Fig. 13). This mine was selected for the first field tests of the UX-1 Robot due to its easy accessibility, clear waters and large tunnel networks without debris. Additionally, the maximum operating depth during tests allowed for the robot to be recovered safely by a scuba-diver in the case of malfunction.

2) ROBOT DEPLOYMENT SYSTEM

The Launch and Recovery System (LRS) installed at the Kaatiala mine site, shown in Fig. 14, was made up of a

FIGURE 14. UX-1 robot being lowered from the launch and recovery platform installed in the Kaatiala mine site.

foldable engine crane with an electric motor hoist. The crane was rigidly attached to the side wall of the quarry and supported up to 300 kg of weight for lowering and raising the robot in between dives.

Once the robot was in the water, the hoist was manually released by a support team from a motor powered inflatable raft in the mine pit. During the tests, as a safety measure, two safety divers were in the water with the robot in communication with the operator mission workstation (Fig. 15).

FIGURE 15. UX-1 robot in the water with two safety divers during initial tests.

3) EXPERIMENTS

The Kaatiala mine was the initial field test site for the UX-1 Robot, this meant that all subsystem functionalities had to be tested before and during the dives. The major components included: the robot battery pack and BMS; filling the oil tank reservoir for the VBS; internal sensor communication; tether cable communication with operator mission workstation; navigation sensor calibration (INS and DVL); and scientific instrumentation calibration and setup (PH, SBP, MSU).

For the Kaatiala Mine dive tests, the VPS component of the motion system was not fully functional. Therefore, the pitch angle throughout all the dives was maintained at $\theta = 0$ rad, which corresponds to a nose front configuration.

Regardless, several tests were performed to validate the depth controller performance and the VBS.

a: VARIABLE BALLAST SYSTEM

The VBS was intended for decreasing the energy consumption during vertical motions, by varying the buoyancy. The initial test with the VBS, shown in Fig. 16, consisted on validating the actual change in the buoyancy of the robot.

FIGURE 16. Variable ballast system initial buoyancy test results.

Since the UX-1 Robot had positive buoyancy by design, water was initially pumped into the cylinders until neutral buoyancy was observed. The robot was then submerged, using the depth controller, until a depth of 15 m was reached. At the 15 m setpoint, the water ballast was purged with the depth controller still engaged, eventually, the depth controller was disengaged and the robot (now positively buoyant) reached the surface without requiring thrust force.

b: DEPTH CONTROL & VARIABLE BALLAST SYSTEM

A similar experiment was performed in order to compare the effects of the VBS on the commanded force, generated by the depth controller, while maintaining the UX-1 Robot at a certain depth with negative and neutral buoyancy.

FIGURE 17. Results of the depth control and VBS force consumption test.

The results for this test are shown in Fig. 17. First, with the robot at the surface, water was pumped into the VBS until negative buoyancy was observed (UX-1 Robot began to sink). Afterwards, the depth controller was activated and the

depth setpoint reference was gradually increased up to 17 m, where it was successfully controlled at this depth with a force close to 5 N. Once the depth was stabilized, the VBS was purged until neutral buoyancy was achieved, thus decreasing the control force required to maintain the same depth to approximately 0 N, before finally commanding to resurface.

c: EXPLORATION

Following the validation of all the available motion systems, an exploration mission of the mine was performed to gather scientific instrumentation measurements from the MSU and the PH sensor, along with 3D point cloud data. For these tests, the VBS was used to trim the buoyancy of the robot during the dive and maintain it as close to neutrally buoyant as possible. In Fig. 18, the UX-1 Robot and a safety diver can be seen during an exploration mission inside a tunnel of the mine.

FIGURE 18. UX-1 robot and safety diver inside mine tunnels during exploration tests.

The UX-1 Robot was submerged by commanding reference setpoints to the FL depth controller, which was active during the entire dive. For the guided exploration, the operator on the surface had control of all other DOF using the HMI peripherals. As can be seen in Fig. 19(f), a max depth of 31 m was achieved, coinciding with the location of the entrance to the mine tunnel; whilst the complete 3D trajectory of the UX-1 Robot during the exploration mission can be seen in Fig. 19(e).

The 3D point clouds of the external wall of the mine, acquired during the dives, are presented in Fig. 19(a) and Fig. 19(b). As can be seen, the two main tunnel entrances are clearly visible from the point cloud data. Furthermore, Fig. 19(c) and Fig. 19(d) show the Octomap [30] representation of the explored section of the mine tunnel with the UX-1 Robot trajectory during the guided exploration mission experiment.

B. IDRİJA MINE, SLOVENIA

1) ENVIRONMENT DESCRIPTION

The Idrija mine is located approximately 60 km west of the capital city of Ljubljana. Mercury deposits in Idrija were first discovered in the late 15th century. Shortly after, the first mining operations began, which continued production for the

FIGURE 19. (a) Front and (b) side views of the 3D pointclouds acquired of the two entrances to the mine tunnels. (c) Side view of the Octomap generated of the tunnel entrance. (d) View of the path of the robot inside the tunnel. (e) Trajectory, (f) Depth and (g) Vertical velocity of the UX-1 robot during the exploration mission.

next 500 years. The mine produced approximately 12.7 Mt of cinnabar ore and 145,000 t of mercury in its 500-year mine life. It is estimated that 13% of total historic worldwide production of mercury came from Idrija. The mine was finally closed in 1995 for commercial, geological, and ecological reasons; nevertheless, some of its shafts and facilities have remained open for tourists.

FIGURE 20. Side view of the levels and sites at the Borba shaft used for the second field tests.

During its production phase, approximately 700 km of tunnels were excavated and the total depth of the mine reached 420 m. The test dives were carried out in the main Borba shaft, seen in Fig. 20, which is currently used by the mine for pumping and regulating the water table. The Idrija mercury mine was selected as the second trial site due to its more challenging environment when compared to the previous test site in Kaatiala; its murky water and confined spaces, provided a perfect place to test the functionality of the UX-1 Robot in very realistic and harsh mine conditions.

2) ROBOT DEPLOYMENT SYSTEM

The Borba shaft was set up with four work sites, two workstations and two LRS platforms at different levels of the mine (see Fig. 20). The operator mission workstation (site 1) was set up on the surface level, 336 m Above Sea Level (ASL). A field workstation (site 2) was set up on

FIGURE 21. UX-1 robot at site 2 in Level III of the Borba shaft.

Level III (214 m ASL), which was accessed from the surface via an elevator, shown in Fig. 21.

The initial part of the LRS consisted of a set of winches to lower the UX-1 Robot approximately 28 m from Level III to Level IV (site 3). On Level IV (187 m ASL), a wooden platform was installed for quick repairs or battery replacement. Afterwards, the UX-1 Robot was switched to a different winch for lowering to the launch platform at Level VI (site 4).

The LRS platform at Level VI (143 m ASL), shown in Fig. 22, was approximately 20 cm above the water level. Due to the restricted air flow, only four people were allowed to work on this platform at the same time. In order to enable communication during launch and recovery, all levels of the shaft were equipped with audio and visual communication with Power-Over-Ethernet (POE) equipment.

FIGURE 22. Deploying the UX-1 robot for a test dive in Idrija mercury mine.

3) EXPERIMENTS

The Idrija mine field experiment objectives, similar to the Kaatiala mine, were to gather mineralogical and structural data from the abandoned mine. Additionally, the performance of the UX-1 Robot was to be assessed in a more challenging environment. To this effect, further testing and validation was

performed on the motion system components of the UX-1 Robot, specifically the heading control and the VPS.

a: VARIABLE PITCH SYSTEM

The VPS was designed to passively stabilize the pitch angle of the UX-1 Robot by rotating the battery module around the central rod using a planetary gear and a stepper motor (see Section II). This rotation was required in order to navigate with the perception sensors, located in the front of the UX-1 Robot, facing towards the direction of movement at all times.

FIGURE 23. Pitch angle results from the tests performed to validate the VPS.

By design, the VPS allowed a pitching motion within the range of $\theta = [-\pi/2, \pi/2]$. However, among these values, three pitch configurations were considered to be essential during normal operations: the Nose Down (ND) configuration ($\theta \approx -\pi/2$), used to descend through vertical mine shafts; the Nose Front (NF) configuration ($\theta = 0$), used to explore side galleries encountered in the shafts; and the Nose Up (NU) configuration ($\theta \approx \pi/2$), applied when an ascent maneuver is performed inside vertical shafts. Fig. 23 shows the results for the VPS stabilization test. All three configurations were tested with the UX-1 Robot at the surface. As can be seen, starting from a negative pitch angle, the VPS was able to complete the setpoints commanded: $\theta = [0, -\pi/2, \pi/2, 0, -\pi/2, 0]$ at $t = [5, 17, 27, 37, 63, 98]$, respectively, with pitch angle feedback from the localization system.

b: DEPTH & HEADING COUPLED CONTROL

The heading control was a crucial component of the motion system. The ability to maintain a constant heading, while navigating through vertical shafts, is an expected exploration maneuver to be performed by the UX-1 Robot in the future. Therefore, the heading control response was tested coupled with the depth controller in a controlled descent and ascent experiment inside the Borba shaft.

For this test, the UX-1 Robot was gradually submerged to a depth of 7.5 m and resurfaced. As can be seen in Fig. 24(a), the depth controller responded as expected, accomplishing all commanded setpoints. The heading controller was activated at the surface, along with the depth control. It remained active throughout the entire dive, where several setpoint references

FIGURE 24. (a) Depth of the UX-1 robot during the coupled control test. (b) Heading control response during the control test with external disturbance.

in heading were sent to test the response of the system, see Fig. 24(b). Additionally, to test the robustness of the control method, an external disturbance (using the joystick interface) was applied to the heading at $t = 76$ s.

c: EXPLORATION

A second controlled dive was performed to explore the deepest section of the Borba shaft and map a drainage gallery, presumably located 30 m bellow water level, at the end of the shaft. During the dive, the VBS was used to maintain neutral buoyancy, the VPS was kept at a NF configuration, and an operator at site 1 guided the exploration. Fig. 25(e) shows the 3D trajectory of the UX-1 Robot all through the dive, as can be seen, the drainage gallery was found at 25 m which was the maximum depth reached (see Fig. 25(f)). Using the pointcloud data from the multibeam and scanning sonars, an Octomap representation of the Borba shaft was obtained. In Fig. 25(a) and Fig. 25(b), the Borba shaft structure and geometry can be seen. Moreover, Fig. 25(c) and Fig. 25(d) show the generated Octomaps of the drainage gallery explored with the UX-1 Robot.

C. URGEIRIÇA MINE, PORTUGAL

1) ENVIRONMENT DESCRIPTION

The Urgeiriça Mine, located in the Viseu district of central Portugal, was considered one of the most important mineral deposits in Europe, mainly due to the exploitation of its strategic commodities. Mining operations began in 1913, focusing at first on the production of Radium. During and after the

FIGURE 25. (a-b) Views of the Octomap representation of the Borba shaft. (c) Top and (d) Side view of the drainage gallery of the main shaft explored at the Idrija Mercury mine. (e) Trajectory, (f) Depth and (g) Vertical velocity of the UX-1 Robot during the exploration mission.

Second world war, the focus was shifted to the extraction of Uranium. In 1971 the conventional cut-and-fill underground mining technique was replaced by the in-situ leaching method before finally ceasing mining operations in 1991.

FIGURE 26. Schematic of the vertical shafts and horizontal tunnels of the Urgeiriça mine, site of the third field trials.

In 1967, the mine reached the maximum depth of approximately 500 m below ground level, comprised of 6 vertical shafts and 19 different depth levels, stretching nearly 1 km in length (see Fig. 26). The Santa Bárbara shaft, were the test dives were performed was 400 m deep with only the first 20 m of the shaft secured with concrete. The Urgeiriça Uranium mine was selected as the third field test site, because it presented similar underwater mine conditions as those found at the Idrija Mercury mine, such as murky waters, confined spaces and obstacles. Moreover, the structures of the vertical shafts allowed testing and validation of the UX-1 Robot systems at bigger depths.

2) ROBOT DEPLOYMENT SYSTEM

The access from the LRS to the water level was much simpler than that at the Idrija Mercury mine. As presented in Fig. 27, the UX-1 Robot was lowered by the LRS into the Santa Bárbara shaft through a 2 m × 2 m opening above the shaft using a 300 kg winch. For safety, the entrance to the shaft was secured with gates and emergency ropes.

FIGURE 27. UX-1 robot being lowered by winch into the Santa Bárbara shaft.

FIGURE 28. UX-1 robot in the water while deploying for a test dive at the third field test.

A launch platform was installed 20 cm above the water level and 8 to 10 m below the surface. The launch platform was accessed by a ladder located on each sidewall of the shaft. Once the UX-1 Robot was prepared for a dive, the LRS was manually released from the launch platform, shown in Fig. 28.

The operator mission workstation was arranged in a storage room/warehouse building only 20 m away from the Santa Bárbara shaft access. Additionally, a field workshop was also available for maintenance work on the UX-1 Robot in between dives.

3) EXPERIMENTS

The objectives for the field experiments at the Urgeiriça Uranium mine were to further test the UX-1 Robot operation in a deep underground mine with accessible entrances to numerous mine levels. The accessibility of the vertical shafts and horizontal tunnels presented the opportunity to test more advanced maneuvering capabilities. As in the previous mine locations, focus was also placed on gathering mineralogical and structural data from the mine. Since the mine was

a Uranium deposit, the scientific instrument for detecting radioactive minerals (i.e. GR) was also tested.

Considering that the main components of the motion system were validated in the previous field experiments, and only initial debugging and tuning had to be performed at the site, the tests performed were mostly focused on exploration dives.

a: EXPLORATION

An exploration mission of the Santa Bárbara shaft was carried out to test the performance of the UX-1 Robot with all the motion systems running simultaneously. During the dive, the VBS was used to maintain the neutral buoyancy of the system; the VPS was used to navigate facing the desired direction of movement; the Heading control was used during the descent and ascent to maintain a constant heading; and the depth controller was used to regulate the commanded depth reference setpoints for the entire duration of the dive.

Fig. 29 presents the response of the motion systems during the exploration mission. The shadowed sections represent stages during the exploration dive that all motion systems were active at the same time. As can be seen in Fig. 29(a), a maximum depth of 106.5 m was reached with the FL depth controller, making this the deepest exploration mission performed.

The descent began with the VPS in a NF configuration and the heading teleoperated from surface, shown in Fig. 29(b) and Fig. 29(c), respectively. With this configuration a depth of approximately 30 m was reached (to eliminate air bubbles in cameras). Thereupon, the VPS configuration was changed to ND and the heading controller was activated, where the controlled submersion continued for another 45 m. Once at 75 m, the VPS was set to a NF configuration and the heading teleoperated in order to explore the Side gallery 3 (see Fig. 30(c)).

After the exploration of the side gallery had been performed, the heading controller was started and the VPS was once again set to a ND configuration. This state was maintained until a depth of 106.5 m was reached by the UX-1 Robot. Eventually, the pitch configuration was set to NF with the heading control off, before finally beginning the ascent with a NU configuration for the VPS and the heading control activated. Finally, when the location for the Side gallery 3 was reached, the VPS was set to a NF configuration with heading control teleoperated and kept this way while resurfacing.

Fig. 30(e) shows the 3D navigation data of the UX-1 Robot during the exploration mission. As can be seen, the side gallery 3 was explored up to 9m from the main shaft. The Octomap of the shaft and side galleries was done by using the pointcloud data from the M3 and Tritech sonars. In Fig. 30(a) and Fig. 30(b), the full view of the Santa Bárbara shaft can be seen along with the side galleries 1, 2, and 3, found during the exploration missions. The side gallery 1 can be seen in Fig. 30(c), whilst the navigation trajectory and the Octomap of side gallery 3 are shown in Fig. 30(d).

FIGURE 29. (a) Depth, (b) Pitch angle, and (c) Heading angle responses of the UX-1 robot during the exploration mission at the Urgeiriça mine. The shadowed sections show when all motion systems were active together.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results from the field experiments are presented and discussed. Table 1 shows a general assessment of the tests performed at each mine site, presenting the overall field experiment details along with a performance analysis of the exploration dives completed.

The inaugural field trials were performed at the Kaatiala mine in Finland. During 11 days of field testing, a total of 10 dives were performed. The initial tests were shallow dives, of up to 15 m depth, in order to test if the communications, scientific instrumentation, external hull watertightness, sensor calibration, and motion systems, were behaving as anticipated. Among these initial tests, the open-loop VBS

FIGURE 30. (a) Full and (b) Side views of the Octomap representation of the Santa Bárbara shaft. (c) Side gallery 1 and (d) Side gallery 3 of the main shaft explored at the Urgeiriça Uranium mine. (e) Trajectory, (f) Roll angle and (g) Vertical velocity of the UX-1 robot during the exploration mission.

TABLE 1. General evaluation of the performance of the system during the three field trials performed.

		Kaa. Mine	Idr. Mine	Urg. Mine
Overall	Trial Period	11 Days	12 Days	19 Days
	Dives Performed	10	11	18
	Mean Duration	0.95 hr	1.10 hr	2.5 hr
	Max Duration	1.69 hr	2.15 hr	3.9 hr
Exploration	Mean Depth	19.67 m	8.53 m	63.69 m
	Max Depth	31.73 m	25.81 m	106.54 m
	Mean Force	1.25 N	0.21 N	3.73 N
	Max Force	119.82 N	43.83 N	24.91 N
	Depth RMSE	0.9094 m	0.2703 m	0.6982 m

motion control component of the UX-1 Robot was tested and validated. The primary objective of the VBS was to achieve a vertical motion of the vehicle without the need for sustained power consumption from the PS. The results of the initial purge test, shown in Fig. 16, demonstrate that the design of the VBS accomplishes the required change in weight needed to control the buoyancy of the UX-1 Robot as a positively or negatively buoyant system. In this test, the UX-1 Robot was surfaced solely by using the added buoyancy provided by purging the VBS with a vertical velocity of 0.375 m/s.

With the VBS design validated as a viable solution for buoyancy control of the UX-1 Robot, a second test was performed to analyze the effect of the VBS on the output force commanded by the FL depth controller to maintain the UX-1 Robot at a required depth. As can be seen in Fig. 17, maintaining a depth of 17 m with a negatively buoyant system required a mean force of 4.11 N from the PS, close to 350 W. After purging the VBS until neutral buoyancy was acquired, the total force commanded by the FL controller for maintaining the same depth lowered to a mean value of 0.20 N, around 4.86% of the initial force. These results show that the addition of the VBS to the UX-1 Robot enhances the overall performance of the motion system by requiring less constant power consumption from the PS, thus extending the overall operational time. Additionally, these tests further validate the FL controller robustness as capable of stabilizing the system to a desired setpoint, even with variations in buoyancy and model parameters.

The final test performed at the Kaatiala mine was an exploration mission, where the results can be seen in Fig 19. The UX-1 Robot was submerged to a max depth of 31.73 m using the PS with the FL depth controller, and the VBS was activated to maintain neutral buoyancy. The response of the FL depth control system is presented Fig. 19(f). Throughout the dive, a mean force of 1.25 N was necessary to stabilize the system to a desired depth with a Root-Mean-Square-Error (RMSE) of 0.9094; whilst a max force of 119.82 N was recorded for a reference command with 15 m difference.

The main objectives of the exploration mission were fulfilled. Mineralogical data was gathered from the scientific

instrumentation, point cloud scans of the mine wall were acquired and Octomaps were generated of the tunnel explored with the UX-1 Robot (see Fig. 19(a) - 19(d)).

With the experience and results obtained at the Kaatiala mine, the second field trials were held at the Idrija Mercury mine in Slovenia. Here, 11 dives were accomplished with an average duration of 1.10 hr to test the main components of the UX-1 Robot that were not validated at the Kaatiala mine, such as the heading control and VPS, as well as performing a complete dive to map the structure of the shaft. In Table 2, the transient and steady-state time response analysis of the tests performed with the heading control and the VPS are presented. The chosen time response metrics were: Overshoot percentage ($OS\%$), Rise time (T_r), Fall time (T_f), Settling time (T_s) and mean error in Steady-State ($meSS$).

TABLE 2. Time response results of the motion control tests performed at the Idrija Mine.

Metrics	Motion System		Units
	VPS Control	Heading Control	
$OS\%$	6.79	1.78	[%]
T_r	5.23	4.60	[s]
T_f	2.05	4.96	[s]
T_s	4.52	6.58	[s]
$meSS$	0.126	0.081	[rad]

A major achievement in the development of the UX-1 Robot was accomplished by testing the VPS inside a real mine shaft. This motion control component was designed to adjust the pitch angle by shifting a mass around the horizontal axis of the vehicle; thus allowing navigation with the front of the UX-1 Robot always pointing towards the desired direction of movement. For the test shown in Fig. 23, the VPS responded to the set points commanded with a T_r of 5.23 s, a T_f of 2.05 s, and a T_s of 4.52 s. These values are considered acceptable for the performance of the VPS, since slow motions are preferred in the confined environments of operation. Nonetheless, for this initial test, the response of the VPS did not reach the expected ND and NU configurations. This was due to improper weight balancing inside the UX-1 Robot which had to be adjusted in order to obtain the full range of motion required in the following field trials.

To accomplish the autonomous navigation expected in the foreseen exploration missions in constrained and unstructured environments, the motion system will require accurate and robust heading control of the UX-1 Robot. As can be seen in Fig. 24, the FL heading controller was successful in maintaining the reference angle setpoints while coupled with the depth controller. During the heading and depth coupled control test, the heading controller produced an $OS\%$ of 1.78% and a $meSS$ of 0.081 rad which are considered desirable responses for the motion control system. Furthermore, the robustness of the heading controller was tested by applying an external disturbance (see Fig. 24(b)) to the

heading of the UX-1 Robot. It can be seen that the controller is able to compensate for this disturbance and stabilize the system with low force and within a reasonable amount of time, i.e., 10 s to compensate for a 1 rad disturbance in heading.

In the exploration dive performed at the Idrija Mercury mine, shown in Fig. 25(e), the UX-1 Robot reached the deepest part of the mine shaft at 25.81 m with exceptional accuracy using the FL depth controller (Fig. 25(f)). For this test, the RMSE obtained was 0.2703 m with a mean force required to stabilize the system of 0.21 N, both substantially lower than in the previous exploration mission at Kaatiala. This difference can be explained by a more accurate tuning of the buoyancy of the UX-1 Robot with the VBS throughout the dive. The duration of the dive was approximately two hours, 1.5 hr for the descent to the bottom of the mine and 0.5 hr for the return to the surface. During the dive, valuable information was collected about the shape of the shaft (Fig. 25(a) and Fig. 25(b)). This included locating an access to a drainage gallery connected to the shaft, that was presumed to be blocked. The mapping data showed that this was not the case, and the side tunnel is open, which was then mapped 7 m into the side gallery (Fig. 25(c) and Fig. 25(d)).

The final field trials were performed at the Urgeiriça uranium mine in Portugal. In total, 18 dives were made over a span of 19 days. The initial dives were used for solving the open issues encountered during the previous field experiments, such as debugging the software, verifying the hardware components, and balancing the internal weight of the UX-1 Robot to improve the range of the VPS. Several exploration dives were carried out to explore the shafts and tunnels of the mine at different depths, with an average duration of 2.5 hr. Moreover, in order to test the endurance of the system, a 3.9 hr deep dive was performed. At the end of the dive, there was enough power left in the system to estimate a maximum operational time of 5.0 hr, which is in accordance with the requirements of the UX-1 Robot [20].

In section V-C3, the deepest exploration mission performed during the field trials can be seen. In this dive, a depth of 106.54 m was reached using the FL depth controller (see Fig. 29(a)) with a RMSE of 0.6982 m and an average required force of 3.73 N. Compared to the exploration dives performed at previous mine sites, the higher accumulated error and force required can be attributed to a greater depth traveled and the weight of the tether cable connected to the robot.

However, this deep dive represented a key milestone in the progress of the motion systems developed for the UX-1 Robot. In the course of the previous field trials, the motion system components had been tested and validated individually, whereas in this exploration mission, for the first time, all the motion systems components were used simultaneously. This achievement raises the readiness level of the UX-1 Robot system towards the goal of achieving fully autonomous exploration missions of flooded mines.

The response of the motion systems for the deep dive can be seen in Fig. 29. The results shown demonstrate that

the VPS, shown in Fig. 29(b), was able to perform the pitching maneuver with the necessary accuracy to navigate through vertical shafts and side galleries in ND, NF or NU configurations; and that the heading control, presented in Fig. 29(c), is able to stabilize the rotation of the UX-1 Robot in any VPS configuration. In this exploration dive, the main shaft and side galleries were explored and mapped (Fig. 30(a) - 30(d)), as well as acquiring video footage, multi-spectral images and UV fluorescence lights of the rock wall, when it was exposed.

Despite the major advances in the development of the UX-1 Robot motion systems in the 39 dives performed, as with any field experiments, several issues were encountered while testing in remote locations. Among these problems, high CPU loads and temperatures were observed, which caused occasional reboots of the on-board main PC. This meant that these parameters had to be constantly monitored during the dives and extra heat dissipation plates installed. The UX-1 Robot was designed and intended to operate as a completely autonomous system. However, not all modules needed for autonomous behavior are ready to be validated in field experiments, e.g. SLAM, which will be the focus of future implementation, testing and validation.

VII. CONCLUSION

The main objective of UX-1 Robot platform is to explore underground mines and to collect geo-scientific and structural data, which will help geologists to better identify future drilling targets. In this work, the UX-1 Robot motion systems have demonstrated successful operation during the field trial exploration missions, performed in the challenging environments of three abandoned and flooded mines across Europe, Kaatiala, Idrija, and Urgeiriça. To the best of our knowledge, these are the first reported field experiments performed in real underground flooded mines.

The mechanical designs of the motion systems integrated into the UX-1 Robot platform, i.e., propulsion system, variable ballast system, and variable pitch system have been presented. Additionally, the system, hardware, and software architectures are explained along with the control method used during dive tests. Moreover, individual field tests have been performed to validate the performance of the motion systems components.

Using the variable pitch system, the ability of the UX-1 Robot to navigate in orientations not usually used for underwater robotics, such as nose down and nose up configurations has been demonstrated. The variable ballast system successfully compensated the buoyancy fluctuation caused by the change in pressure at different depths; whilst the state Feedback Linearization control method, tested in water tanks in previous works, was able to control the depth and heading of the UX-1 Robot during dives of more than 100 m depth. Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that all of the motion systems are capable of working simultaneously during an exploration mission of the Santa Bárbara shaft at the Urgeiriça mine. All subsystems were tested in real

environment, for which we can state that a TRL of 5 has been successfully reached. The whole system has also been tested (TRL 6) with success, although more extensive tests are needed to claim full success at this level.

Based on the results and lessons learned from the field experiments presented in this work, the future work for the UX-1 Robot platform focus on increasing the autonomy level. This involves testing the use of solely the variable ballast system for depth control, the integration and validation of SLAM algorithms and the development of cooperative exploration techniques. A fourth field trial is planned at the historical copper mine Ecton in the UK. The objective of the final trial is to conduct a detailed survey of the entire Ecton mine using two robots, that are going to be exploring the mine simultaneously.

Extensive interest from the scientific community and media coverage were present during the field trials with more than 30 appearances in Slovenian media including TV Slovenia 1, and appearances in Portuguese media such as national television stations SIC and RTP. Additionally, a Euronews story about UNEXMIN aired on Euronews science and technology program Futuris in 12 different languages. The English version of the program is available at: <http://www.euronews.com/2018/07/02/how-a-robot-in-deep-water-can-bring-enlightenment>.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Didier, "Mine closure and post-mining management international state-of-the-art," Int. Soc. Rock Mech., Lisbon, Portugal, Tech. Rep. 1, Jun. 2008. [Online]. Available: https://www.ineris.fr/sites/ineris.fr/files/contribution/Documents/CDi__mineclosure_29_11_08-ang.pdf
- [2] K. B. Ånonsen, O. K. Hagen, and E. Berglund, "Autonomous mapping with AUVs using relative terrain navigation," in *Proc. OCEANS*, Anchorage, AK, USA, Sep. 2017, pp. 1–7.
- [3] C. Roman and H. Singh, "A self-consistent bathymetric mapping algorithm," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 24, nos. 1–2, pp. 23–50, 2007.
- [4] C. White, D. Hiranandani, C. S. Olstad, K. Buhagiar, T. Gambin, and C. M. Clark, "The Malta cistern mapping project: Underwater robot mapping and localization within ancient tunnel systems," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 27, pp. 399–411, Jul./Aug. 2010.
- [5] D. Hiranandani, C. White, C. Clark, T. Gambin, and K. Buhagiar, "Underwater robots with sonar and smart tether for underground cistern mapping and exploration," in *Proc. 10th Int. Symp. Virtual Reality, Archaeology Cultural Heritage VAST*, Malta, U.K., Sep. 2009, pp. 1–5.
- [6] A. Mallios, P. Ridaou, M. Carreras, and E. Hernández, "Navigating and mapping with the SPARUS AUV in a natural and unstructured underwater environment," in *Proc. OCEANS KONA*, Waikoloa, HI, USA, Sep. 2011, pp. 1–7.
- [7] A. Mallios, P. Ridaou, D. Ribas, M. Carreras, and R. Camilli, "Toward autonomous exploration in confined underwater environments," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 33, pp. 994–1012, Oct. 2016.
- [8] N. Fairfield, G. Kantor, and D. Wettergreen, "Real-time SLAM with otree evidence grids for exploration in underwater tunnels," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 24, pp. 3–21, Jan./Feb. 2007.
- [9] M. Gary, N. Fairfield, W. C. Stone, D. Wettergreen, G. A. Kantor, and J. M. Sharp, "3D mapping and characterization of sistema Zacatón from DEPTHX (DEep Phreatic THERmal eXplorer)," in *Proc. 11th Sinkhole Conf. ASCE KARST*, Tallahassee, FL, USA, Sep. 2008, pp. 22–24.
- [10] N. Fairfield, D. Jonak, G. A. Kantor, and D. Wettergreen, "Field results of the control, navigation, and mapping systems of a hovering AUV," in *Proc. Unmanned Untethered Submersible Technol. Conf.*, Jan. 2007, pp. 20–22.
- [11] B. E. Schmidt et al., "Sub-ice marine and planetary ecosystems: First results from below the McMurdo ice shelf," in *Proc. Astrobiol. Sci. Conf.*, Chicago, IL, USA, Jun. 2015, pp. 15–19.
- [12] K. Richmond, S. Gulati, C. Flesher, B. P. Hogan, and W. C. Stone, "Navigation, control, and recovery of the ENDURANCE under-ice hovering AUV," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Unmanned Untethered Submersible Technol. (UUST)*, 2009, pp. 1–12.
- [13] S. Gulati, K. Richmond, C. Flesher, B. P. Hogan, A. Murarka, G. Kuhlmann, M. Sridharan, W. C. Stone, and P. T. Doran, "Toward autonomous scientific exploration of ice-covered lakes—Field experiments with the ENDURANCE AUV in an Antarctic Dry Valley," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Automat.*, Anchorage, AK, USA, May 2010, pp. 308–315.
- [14] F. Cazenave, R. Zook, D. Carroll, M. Flagg, and S. Kim, "Development of the ROV SCINI and deployment in McMurdo sound, Antarctica," *J. Ocean Technol.*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 39–58, 2011.
- [15] J. Burnett, F. Rack, B. Zook, and B. Schmidt, "Development of a borehole deployable remotely operated vehicle for investigation of sub-ice aquatic environments," in *Proc. OCEANS Washington*, Washington, DC, USA, Oct. 2015, pp. 1–7.
- [16] A. Spears, M. West, M. Meister, J. Buffo, C. Walker, T. R. Collins, A. Howard, and B. Schmidt, "Under ice in Antarctica: The Icefin unmanned underwater vehicle development and deployment," *IEEE Robot. Autom. Mag.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 30–41, Dec. 2016.
- [17] C. Moore and P. McKibbin, "Artemis AUV payload development," in *Proc. OCEANS Washington*, Washington, DC, USA, Oct. 2015, pp. 1–3.
- [18] P. W. Kimball, E. B. Clark, M. Scully, K. Richmond, C. Flesher, L. E. Lindzey, J. Harman, K. Huffstutler, J. Lawrence, S. Lelievre, J. Moor, B. Pease, V. Siegel, L. Winslow, D. D. Blankenship, P. Doran, S. Kim, B. E. Schmidt, and W. C. Stone, "The ARTEMIS under-ice AUV docking system," *J. Field Robot.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 299–308, 2018.
- [19] K. Richmond, C. Flesher, L. Lindzey, N. Tanner, and W. C. Stone, "SUNFISH: A human-portable exploration AUV for complex 3D environments," in *Proc. OCEANS Charleston*, Charleston, SC, USA, Oct. 2018, pp. 1–9.
- [20] L. Lopes, N. Zajzon, B. Bodo, S. Henley, G. Žibret, and T. Dizdarevic, "UNEXMIN: Developing an autonomous underwater explorer for flooded mines," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 125, pp. 41–49, Sep. 2017.
- [21] S. Zavari, A. Heininen, J. Aaltonen, and K. T. Koskinen, "Early stage design of a spherical underwater robotic vehicle," in *Proc. IEEE 20th Int. Conf. Syst. Theory, Control Comput. (ICSTCC)*, Oct. 2016, pp. 240–244.
- [22] J. Villa, A. Heininen, S. Zavari, T. Salomaa, O. Usenius, J. Laitinen, J. Aaltonen, and K. T. Koskinen, "Mechanical subsystems integration and structural analysis for the autonomous underwater explorer," in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst. (IROS)*, Madrid, Spain, Oct. 2018, pp. 1488–1493.
- [23] A. Martins, J. Almeida, C. Almeida, A. Dias, N. Dias, J. Aaltonen, A. Heininen, K. T. Koskinen, C. Rossi, S. Dominguez, C. Vörös, S. Henley, M. McLoughlin, H. van Moerkerk, J. Tweedie, B. Bodo, N. Zajzon, and E. Silva, "UX 1 system design—A robotic system for underwater mining exploration," in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst. (IROS)*, Madrid, Spain, Oct. 2018, pp. 1494–1500.
- [24] R. A. S. Fernandez, D. Grande, A. Martins, L. Bascetta, S. Dominguez, and C. Rossi, "Modeling and control of underwater mine explorer robot UX-1," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 39432–39447, 2019.
- [25] B. Sumantr, M. N. Karsiti, and H. Agustian, "Development of variable ballast mechanism for depth positioning of spherical URV," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Inf. Technol.*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Aug. 2008, pp. 1–6.
- [26] T. I. Fossen, *Handbook of Marine Craft Hydrodynamics and Motion Control*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2011.
- [27] The Society of Naval Architects and Marine Engineers, "Nomenclature for treating the motion of a submerged body through a fluid," Soc. Nav. Archit. Mar. Eng., New York, NY, USA, Tech. Res. Bull. 1–5, Apr. 1950. [Online]. Available: <https://www.itk.ntnu.no/fag/TTK4190/papers/Sname%201950.PDF>
- [28] T. Fossen, "Nonlinear modeling and control of underwater vehicles," Ph.D. dissertation, Dept. Eng. Cybern., Norwegian Univ. Sci. Technol., Trondheim, Norway, 1991.
- [29] Y. Chen and J. Wang, "A global optimization algorithm for energy-efficient control allocation of over-actuated systems," in *Proc. Amer. Control Conf. (ACC)*, Jun./Jul. 2011, pp. 5300–5305.
- [30] A. Hornung, K. M. Wurm, M. Bennewitz, C. Stachniss, and W. Burgard, "OctoMap: An efficient probabilistic 3D mapping framework based on octrees," *Auton. Robots*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 189–206, 2013.

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